

Comparative Analysis of Evolutionary Algorithms for Optimizing Vehicle Routing in Smart Cities

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Abstract: This paper presents a comparative analysis of evolutionary algorithms, including genetic algorithms, particle swarm optimization, cuckoo algorithm, and the Harris Hawk Optimization algorithm, for optimizing vehicle routing in smart cities. The study evaluates the performance of these algorithms in minimizing costs and maximizing efficiency in the context of providing services to requesters. Results indicate the effectiveness of the Harris Hawk Optimization algorithm compared to other approaches, suggesting its suitability for real-world applications in smart city environments. Future directions for research in this area are also discussed.

Keywords: Evolutionary algorithms, Vehicle routing, Smart cities, Optimization, Comparative analysis

1. Introduction

Smart transportation has emerged as an indispensable necessity and solution in today's traffic-congested cities. Urbanization presents significant challenges, including traffic congestion, pollution, and inefficiencies in transportation systems. In response to these challenges, smart cities have been developed, leveraging Information and Communication Technology (ICT) to promote sustainable development approaches[1].

A fundamental aspect of smart cities is the implementation of intelligent transportation systems, which optimize vehicle routing to minimize congestion, reduce travel time, and enhance overall efficiency. Evolutionary algorithms have gained prominence as effective tools for addressing complex optimization problems in smart transportation systems[2].

This research focuses on improving vehicle routing in smart cities using evolutionary algorithms, with a particular emphasis on the Hybrid Harris's Hawks Optimization (HHO) algorithm[3]. The HHO algorithm is a gradient-independent optimization technique inspired by the cooperative behavior and agile pursuit of Harris's Hawks in nature, known as the "surprise pounce."

The main objective of this study is to investigate the effectiveness of the HHO algorithm in optimizing vehicle routing within smart cities. By simulating the behavior of Harris's Hawks, which exhibit diverse patterns of pursuit and evasion, the HHO algorithm aims to find optimal routes for vehicles in dynamic urban environments.

To evaluate the performance of the HHO algorithm, extensive comparisons are made with other nature-inspired techniques and traditional optimization methods. Statistical analysis and comparisons are conducted on a set of 29 functions and several real-world engineering problems to assess the algorithm's effectiveness in improving vehicle routing efficiency.

Furthermore, this research explores the broader context of smart cities, highlighting key components such as smart transportation, smart lighting, smart parking, smart agriculture, smart waste management, and smart buildings. These components illustrate the interconnectedness of ICT-enabled systems in urban environments, offering opportunities for enhancing sustainability, reducing costs, and improving quality of life.

In conclusion, this paper contributes to the growing body of literature on smart transportation and evolutionary algorithms by providing insights into the application of the HHO algorithm for optimizing vehicle routing in smart cities. The findings of this research have implications for urban planners, policymakers, and researchers seeking to address the challenges of urbanization through innovative ICT solutions.

Literature review:

In [4], the "Selective Routing with Vehicle Routing and Pricing" is introduced, modeled, and solved. Considering the routing costs using a homogeneous fleet of vehicles, optimal pricing is addressed. In the mentioned study, an improved colonial competitive algorithm is utilized, and several samples are solved in small dimensions to compare the validity of this method in problem-solving. The obtained results from a precise method and a simulated annealing algorithm are compared. To examine the algorithm's efficiency in real dimensions, several samples are solved by both algorithms, and the results are compared. Computational results indicate the suitable performance of the proposed method in problem-solving.

In [5], the integrated scheduling of production and distribution with vehicle routing is examined. A factory with multiple parallel production lines receives customer orders. After producing the ordered products, they are batched and sent to customers via a fleet of vehicles. Unlike the direct shipment method from the factory to each customer, batch shipment reduces transportation costs due to maximum utilization of transportation capacity but may lead to increased maintenance costs and delays. The objective is to find an integrated production and distribution schedule to minimize preparation, maintenance, distribution, and delay costs. Initially, the problem is modeled as a mixed integer linear programming model. Due to its NP-hard nature, a combined algorithm of colonial competitive and dominance rules is proposed to solve large-scale problems. To evaluate the performance of the proposed algorithm, several

sample problems are generated and solved. Computational results indicate that the algorithm performs well for large-scale problems.

In [6], intelligent transportation systems aimed at providing services to vehicle drivers are discussed. In these networks, route optimization is the most crucial issue due to the movement pattern and high speed of vehicles. Clustering-based routing protocols are used in the mentioned study. In clustering, selecting the appropriate cluster head is of utmost importance, with priority given to a node that can cover more vehicles and is available for a longer duration. Another important issue is the creation and maintenance of cluster heads, which is unavoidable due to the high speed of vehicles, constant connection disruptions, and significant topology changes. In this research, for proper cluster head selection and intelligent clustering, a set of basic criteria such as proximity, density, speed, and direction of vehicle movement is considered, and a neural network-based training method is used for delay optimization. The result of this operation is a score for each vehicle, indicating its suitability for clustering. The use of artificial neural networks aligns with the need to calculate appropriate weights for each criterion and offline weight calculation with problem conditions. According to the simulation results of the mentioned research, the proposed algorithm has reduced end-to-end delay and increased package delivery rates compared to other compared algorithms.

Due to the challenge of finding suitable routes during peak traffic hours and with traffic restrictions in place, which not only leads to suboptimal performance in distribution networks but also imposes irreparable environmental damage on society, [7] focuses on improving the routing of goods distribution networks using intelligent transportation systems. In this regard, after modeling the problem in the form of vehicle routing problem development considering traffic constraints and time windows, and its NP-hard nature, the problem was solved using a combination of genetic algorithms and particle swarm optimization algorithms. The optimal routes and the number of vehicles needed for cargo delivery were determined. Based on this, initially, customer locations were clustered based on delivery time windows using clustering algorithms, then a user interface was provided to receive the origin and destination from the user, and this interface retrieves the available routes between the origin and destination from the Google Maps. Proposed routes are generated using the proposed algorithms, and in case of events such as traffic, the vehicle deviates from the route using network routing protocols. The proposed method has shown better results in terms of minimizing distance and the number of vehicles compared to optimal solutions.

In [8], six scenarios based on intelligent transportation were designed and implemented. In the first scenario, the process of monitoring and controlling vehicle speed, in the second and third scenarios, the processes of monitoring vehicles at the entrance and traffic circulation in traffic zones and even and odd, in the fourth scenario, the process of monitoring vehicles in case of vehicle malfunctions and intelligent notification to the car rescue system, in the fifth scenario, the emergency assistance system in accidents and informing the emergency center, and in the sixth scenario[9], the intelligent vehicle monitoring system and notification and sending

messages to the owner and police forces during and after vehicle theft were designed and implemented. The message sending process has been implemented to fully cover the smart city area so that, if necessary, all vehicles involved in the intelligent transportation process receive the message [10]. The first challenge of the mentioned research was the selection of fixed target nodes, which was designed and implemented using the fuzzy-ranked fuzzy-logic-based planning algorithm. After solving the first challenge, considering the communication range problem in the vehicle network [11], the message routing challenge from the access point to the fixed target node was raised, which was addressed using the Dijkstra algorithm. After simulation, the results obtained were compared with the eTGMD algorithm in terms of message delivery rate, delivery delay, number of consumed package transmissions, and number of fixed target nodes, and the results of the proposed algorithm showed significant improvement and optimization compared to the eTGMD algorithm[12,13].

New and his colleagues attempted to optimize the problem of open green car routing with time windows by minimizing routing costs. They designed a hybrid taboo search algorithm containing several neighborhood search strategies to solve this problem and conducted computational experiments on real-world samples based on actual conditions of Beijing roads[14], China. Compared to closed routes, open routes reduced overall costs by up to 20% in fuel emission costs and approximately 30% in carbon dioxide emission costs [15,19].

Jiang and his colleagues used a particle swarm optimization algorithm for the vehicle routing problem with time windows. The vehicle routing problem with time windows has two objectives: minimizing the number of vehicles and minimizing the total travel distance. Most algorithms focus on the number of vehicles, while travel distance should be considered as the main objective in some practical applications, especially in modern logistics. Their research showed that designing a systematic framework for combining multiple algorithms with different characteristics significantly improves the overall performance of the hybrid algorithm [20,21].

Mousavi Tabar and his colleagues attempted to assess and compare various books and articles, reputable journal publications in the field of vehicle routing, examining their strengths and weaknesses [22].

Mofakhkhar and his colleagues present a mathematical model for the dynamic problem of determining the number of freight wagons. The model attempts to encompass real-world conditions and constraints as much as possible. In the presented model, demand for wagons and travel time are considered deterministic. Since there are multiple objectives in the real world, another objective function has been considered in this research to increase efficiency, reducing the number of delays in responding to demands throughout the planning period. According to real-world railroad conditions, heterogeneous freight wagons are considered. Also, for the first time in the presented model, three constraints of vehicle capacity, vehicle dispatch, and line capacity are considered. Allocating empty wagons to increase the utilization

of existing wagons in the network and consequently reducing a significant amount of fleet ownership and maintenance costs has become a notable aspect. In this article, after defining the problem, the relevant mathematical model is presented. A multi-objective simulated annealing algorithm-based approach is presented to find Pareto solutions. Finally, a numerical example taken from the rail transport industry of the Islamic Republic of Iran is solved and discussed [23].

Methodology:

This research, in terms of research classification based on its objective, is of a practical nature. The executive steps of the research are as follows:

Complete study and understanding of smart cities, the Internet of Things, intelligent transportation systems, and evolutionary algorithms.

Presentation of the research model.

Evaluation and analysis of the obtained results.

Advancement and development in intelligent transportation systems, considering the specified needs from the service recipients, still face challenges because the massive volume of service requests and the capability of delivery are not balanced. Therefore, various methods and techniques are presented to establish this mutual balance. In the context of the Internet of Things and the discussion of smartification in smart cities, transportation systems are one of the important areas. Hence, considerable attention has been paid to this area. However, only a few solutions have been proposed for optimizing the routing of transportation vehicles dependent on time in these networks. Therefore, in this research, an architecture is proposed to address this significant challenge using the Shahin Harris optimization algorithm. In this manner, the data of locations and vehicles are transmitted to the communication management center using data transmission technologies and sensor data, which are then stored in a unified online database. In this phase, parallel data mining is performed based on defined needs, and knowledge extraction tailored to the requirements is carried out. In this research, the Shahin Harris algorithm is utilized to reduce costs, and the proposed method is implemented using MATLAB tools.

The Multi-Depot Multi-Trip Vehicle Routing Problem with Direct Delivery can be formulated as a mixed integer programming model. Before presenting the model, the symbols used to describe the model according to Table (1) are provided.

Table 1: Symbols Used to Describe the Proposed Method

Description	Symbol	Description	Symbol
Amount of service type p sent from service provider to distribution center j during period t	I_{max_j}	Indicate sub-service providers	p
Cost of sending service from service provider to sub-service provider	d_{pit}	Demand value of service type p at sub-service provider j in period t	j
Amount of service type p produced during period t by the service provider	P_{max}	Planning periods indicator	t
Capacity utilization coefficient of service type p from storage space or service vehicle	Q	Service provider capacity for service provision	N
Binary variable indicating whether service is sent from sub-service provider j in period t	h_{pj}	Number of sub-service providers	f_t
Capacity utilization coefficient of service provision by service provider type p	w_{pit}	Transport capacity	I_{pit}
Binary variable indicating service production in period t	P_{pt}	Fixed cost of setting up service for the service provider in period t	c_j
The variable zero and one indicate the service delivery to the server except J in the period T	X_{jt}	Maintenance cost of one unit of service type p at center j	a_p
Variable zero and one indicator of service production in period T	Z_t	Amount of service type p in period t at center j	k_p

The mathematical model of the problem is presented using equations (1) to (8).

Equation (1) represents the objective function of the proposed model, which includes the fixed setup costs, the cost of delivering the service to the sub-service providers, and the maintenance costs incurred by both the service provider and the sub-service providers.

$$\min Z = \sum_t f_t \cdot Z_t + \sum_{t,j|j \neq 0} c_j \cdot X_{jt} + \sum_{p,j,t} h_{pj} \cdot I_{pit} \quad (1)$$

Equation (2) expresses the balance of acceptance between the demand for service type p at sub-service provider j in period t and the total service type p delivered from the service provider to sub-service provider l in period t.

$$I_{pj(t-1)} + w_{pj} - I_{pj} = d_{pj} \quad \forall p, j \mid j \neq 0, t \quad (2)$$

The balance between the total service type p delivered from the service provider to all sub-service providers in period t and the total service type p produced in period t is expressed using Equation (3).

$$I_{p0(t-1)} + P_{pt} - I_{p0t} = \sum_j w_{pj} \quad \forall p, t \quad (3)$$

Equation (4) ensures the capacity constraint for acceptance and service.

$$\sum_p k_p \cdot P_{pt} \leq P_{\max} \cdot Z_t \quad \forall t \quad (4)$$

The capacity constraint of transportation vehicles is presented using Equation (5). Equations (3-4) and (3-5) implicitly indicate whether production has occurred by the service provider in period t or if a service has been sent to subcontractor j in period t.

$$\begin{aligned} & \forall j \mid j \neq 0, t \\ & \sum_p a_p \cdot w_{pj} \leq Q \cdot X_{jt} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Equation (6) ensures the capacity maintenance constraint for both the service provider and subcontractors.

$$\sum_p a_p \cdot I_{pj} \leq \text{Imax}_j \quad \forall j, t \quad (6)$$

Technical constraints on decision variables are enforced through equations (7) and (8).

$$X_{jt}, Z_t \in \{0,1\} \quad \forall j, t \quad (7)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \forall p, j, t \\ & P_{pt}, w_{pj}, I_{pj} \geq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

The application of the HHO algorithm can be divided into two phases:

1. **Exploration Phase:** In this phase, the exploration mechanism of the HHO algorithm is introduced. Considering the nature of Harris's Hawks, these birds can identify and track prey using their powerful eyes. However, prey is not always easily visible. Therefore, Harris's Hawks typically perch and surveil the desert for hours until they identify their prey. In HHO, Harris's Hawks correspond to candidate solutions, and the best candidate solution at each stage is considered as the prey near the optimal point. In HHO, Harris's Hawks perch randomly at some points according to two strategies and wait for prey identification. If we consider equal chance q for perching for each strategy, Harris's Hawks select their perching locations based on the positions of other family members (close enough) and also the position of the rabbit. This strategy is modeled in equation (9) for $q < 0.5$. Another strategy is for Harris's Hawks to randomly perch on tall trees (random points in their territory). This strategy is also modeled in equation (9) for $q \geq 0.5$.

$$X(t+1) = \begin{cases} x_{rand}(t) - r_1 | x_{rand}(t) - 2r_2x(t) | & q \geq 0.5 \\ x_{rabbit}(t) - x_m(t) - r_3(LB + r_4(UB - LB)) & q < 0.5 \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

In this equation, $X(t+1)$ represents the vector of positions of the Harris's Hawks in the next iteration after t , $X_{rabbit}(t)$ denotes the position of the rabbit, $X(t)$ denotes the current vector of positions of the Harris's Hawks, r_1 , r_2 , r_3 , r_4 , and q are random numbers in the interval $(0, 1)$. Random numbers are updated in each iteration. LB and UB respectively denote the lower and upper bounds of the variables, $X_{rand}(t)$ is a randomly selected Harris's Hawk from the current population. X_m also represents the mean position of the Harris's Hawks in the current population. In the proposed solution, the values of zero and one are used to represent the time of sending services to different sub-service providers and the time of production. Each one indicates the production or sending of services to the sub-service provider in that period, and zero indicates the lack of service provision or sending services in that period.

We provide a simple model for generating random locations within the territory (LB, UB) . The first rule generates responses based on a random position as well as the positions of other Harris's Hawks. In the second rule, equation (3-9), we obtain the difference between the best position found so far and the group mean position plus a portion randomly scaled based on the variable domain. r_3 is a scaling factor used to increase randomness as r_4 approaches 1. In this rule, we add a random scale displacement to LB , then consider a random scaling factor for further biased exploration and search different regions in the feature space. It is possible to create various update rules, but here we employ the simplest rule to simulate the behavior of Harris's Hawks based on it. We can obtain the mean position of Harris's Hawks using equation (10):

$$X_m(t) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N X_i(t) \quad (10)$$

In this equation, $X_i(t)$ represents the position of each hawk in one iteration, and N represents the number of hawks. The mean position can be obtained by various methods, but here we use the simplest rule.

Transition from the exploration phase to the exploitation phase: The HHO algorithm can transition from the exploration phase to the exploitation phase, and then adopt different

exploitation behaviors based on the prey's escape energy. The energy of prey significantly decreases during the escape. To model this issue, the prey's energy is modeled as follows:

$$E=2E_0(1 - \frac{t}{T}) \quad (11)$$

In this equation, E represents the escape energy of the prey, T denotes the maximum number of iterations, and E0 denotes the initial energy of the prey. In HHO, the value of E0 changes randomly in the interval (-1, 1) in each iteration. When the value of E0 decreases from 0 to -1, it means that the prey's escape energy is weakening, while increasing this value from 0 to 1 indicates strengthening the prey's escape energy. The escape energy E has a decreasing trend over the iterations. When the escape energy $|E| \geq 1$, the hawks search different regions to discover the rabbit's position (a task performed in the HHO algorithm). When the escape energy $|E| < 1$, the algorithm tries to identify the vicinity of the solutions during the exploitation steps. In summary, the exploration operation occurs when $|E| \geq 1$, while exploitation operations occur in subsequent steps when $|E| < 1$.

2. Extraction phase

In this phase, the Harris's hawks perform a surprise attack on the identified prey from the previous phase. Although the prey typically tries to escape from dangerous situations, different tactics are employed for hunting in real-life scenarios. Based on the evasion behaviors of the prey and the pursuit strategies of the Harris's hawks, four strategies are proposed in the HHO algorithm to model the attack process.

The prey always attempts to escape from threatening conditions. Let r represent the probability of successful escape ($r < 0.5$) or unsuccessful escape ($r \geq 0.5$) before the surprise attack. The prey's actions lead the Harris's hawks to perform either a hard or soft encirclement operation to capture the prey, depending on the remaining energy of the prey. This means that the Harris's hawks surround the prey from different directions based on its remaining energy. In real-life situations, the Harris's hawks approach closer and closer to the prey to increase the chance of a surprise attack. To model this strategy and incorporate the capability of transitioning between hard and soft encirclement processes in HHO, the parameter E is utilized. Accordingly, when $|E| \geq 0.5$, a soft encirclement occurs, and when $|E| < 0.5$, a hard encirclement takes place. During soft encirclement, when $r \geq 0.5$, the prey (rabbit) still has sufficient energy and tries to confuse the Harris's hawks with random hops. During these attempts, the Harris's hawks softly surround the prey, wearing the rabbit down, and then launch a surprise attack. This behavior is modeled based on the following rules.

$$X(t+1) = \Delta X(t) - E|Jx_{rabbit}(t) - x_m(t)| \quad (12)$$

$$\Delta X(t) = x_{rabbit}(t) - x_m(t) \quad (13)$$

In this equation, $\Delta X(t)$ represents the difference between the rabbit's position vector and the current position in iteration t. Additionally, r5 is a random number in the range (0,1), and $J=2(1-r5)$ indicates the strength of the rabbit's random hops during the escape process. The value of J changes randomly in each iteration to simulate the natural conditions of rabbit movements.

During hard encirclement, when $r \geq 0.5$ and $|E| < 0$, the prey is tired, and its escape energy is low. Furthermore, the Harris's hawks tightly encircle the prey to eventually execute a surprise attack. In these conditions, the current states are updated using equation (14).

$$X(t + 1) = x_{rabbit}(t) - E|\Delta X(t)| \quad (14)$$

In the soft encirclement with fast dives, when $|E| \geq 0.5$ and $r < 0.5$, the rabbit still has enough energy to escape and continues to utilize the soft encirclement before the surprise attack. This strategy is more intelligent than the previous one.

To mathematically model the patterns of prey evasion and "zigzag movements," the concept of "Lévy Flight" (LF) is employed in the HHO algorithm. The Lévy Flight technique is used to represent deceptive zigzag movements of the prey during the escape phase and the extraordinary and rapid dives of the hawks around the prey. Multiple fast diving hawks surround the rabbit and try to adjust their position and direction based on the deceptive movements of the prey. Studies suggest that Lévy Flight-based operations are considered optimal tactics for predators in non-destructive conditions. Additionally, research indicates that Lévy Flight patterns can be identified in the hunting behavior of animals such as monkeys and sharks. Therefore, in this phase of the HHO method, Lévy Flight movements are utilized.

Inspired by the real behavior of hawks, we assume that hawks, when capturing prey in competitive situations, aim for the best dive possible toward the prey. Therefore, to execute soft encirclement, we assume that hawks can evaluate their next move based on the rule described in equation (15).

$$Y = x_{rabbit}(t) - E|x_{rabbit}(t) - X(t)| \quad (15)$$

They then compare the potential outcomes with the previous dive to determine whether the next move (dive) can be a good one or not. If the next move is deemed unreasonable (when they observe that the prey is making more deceptive movements), they also resort to unusual and rapid dives as they approach the rabbit. We assume that they will dive based on the following rule using LF patterns.

$$Z = Y + S \times LF(D) \quad (16)$$

In this equation, D represents the dimension of the problem, and S is a random vector with size $1 \times D$. In this context, LF denotes the Levi Flight, which is calculated using equation (17).

$$LF(x) = 0.01 \times \frac{u \times \sigma}{|v|^{\frac{1}{\beta}}}, \sigma = \left(\frac{\Gamma(1 + \beta) \times \sin(\frac{\pi\beta}{2})}{\Gamma(\frac{1+\beta}{2}) \times \beta \times 2^{(\frac{\beta-1}{2})}} \right)^{\frac{1}{\beta}} \quad (17)$$

In this equation, u and v are random values in the interval (0,1). β is a constant value equal to 1.5. Based on this, the final strategy for updating the positions of the falcons in the soft

besieging phase is done according to the fitting function equation (9) as expressed in equation (18)

$$X(t+1) = \begin{cases} Y & \text{if } (F(Y) < F(X(t))) \\ Z & \text{if } (F(Z) < F(X(t))) \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

In this equation, Y and Z are calculated using equations (15) and (16). In the improved hard besieging phase with rapid dashes, when $|E| < 0.5$ and $r < 0.5$, the rabbit will not have enough energy to escape, and in these conditions, before the ambush attack, hard besieging is performed. In this phase, the situation on the prey side is similar to soft besieging, but this time, the falcons try to reduce the distance between their average positions and the prey. Therefore, in hard besieging conditions, the following rule is applied:

$$X(t+1) = \begin{cases} Y & \text{if } (F(Y) < F(X(t))) \\ Z & \text{if } (F(Z) < F(X(t))) \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

In this equation, Y and Z are calculated using the following new rules:

$$Y = x_{rabbit}(t) - E |x_{rabbit}(t) - X_m(t)| \quad (20)$$

$$Z = Y + S \times LF(D) \quad (21)$$

In this equation, $X_m(t)$ is calculated using the formula (10).

Results:

In the figure below, the schematic of the system under study for evaluation is shown.

Figure 1. Schematic of the system under study for evaluation.

There are various sections connected over the Internet of Things (IoT) platform with the help of BTS and WIFI, including locations such as hospitals, gas stations, sports stadiums, gas pumps, parking lots, cars, traffic lights, residential homes, etc. Each section transmits specific data such as location, conditions, and status according to defined needs to the communication management and monitoring center. Finally, the central system, based on the received and sensed data, manages traffic and controls it using various tools. Here, a quick guide and route planner for moving objects (vehicles) have been developed based on various geographical conditions, traffic situations, different facility conditions including availability and capacity for service provision, and other various factors using the Harris Hawk optimization algorithm. The details of the algorithm stages are explained in Chapter Three. In this study, the algorithm iteration number is considered to be 10, 25, and 50. According to the results, the performance was better with 25 iterations, and therefore, the results of this iteration are presented as the evaluation outcome here.

For comparison, optimization algorithms such as Genetic Algorithm, Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO), and Tabu Search have also been used. A brief explanation of each of these algorithms is provided below.

1- Genetic Algorithm: Mr. Goldberg was able to present the framework and rules governing the genetic algorithm by publishing the book "Genetic Algorithms in Search, Optimization, and Machine Learning" in 1989, and the convergence of the genetic algorithm was established in 1990. Genetic algorithms are heuristic search and optimization algorithms that are executed in parallel and are inspired by the principles of natural selection and genetic reproduction proposed by Darwin. In other words, these algorithms are optimization techniques based on selection and recombination of promising solutions. The purpose of applying genetic algorithms to these problems is to investigate the capability of this algorithm in obtaining optimal solutions and also to examine its convergence and performance under different settings. In traditional genetic algorithms, solutions are represented as binary strings of 0s and 1s. Encodings can be binary or real depending on the type of problem. A general framework for the genetic algorithm can be pseudo-coded as follows:

```
Create initial population of size n;  
repeat  
{  
  for i=1 to k  
  {  
    choose parent1 and parent2 from the  
    population;  
    offspringi ← crossover(parent1,parent2);  
    offspringi ← mutation(offspringi);  
  }  
  replace(population,  
  [offspring1, offspring2, offspringk]);  
} until (stopping condition);  
return the best solution;
```


2. Particle Swarm Optimization Algorithm: The Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) algorithm is a social-based search algorithm modeled after the collective behavior of bird flocks. Initially, this algorithm was employed to discover the governing patterns of simultaneous bird flights, sudden changes in their trajectory, and optimal flock formation. In PSO, particles move in the current search space, and their movement is influenced by their own experience, knowledge, and that of their neighbors. Therefore, the position of other particles in the swarm affects the search behavior of a particle. The result of modeling this social behavior is a search process where particles tend towards successful regions. Particles learn from each other and move towards the best neighbor based on the knowledge gained. The basis of the PSO algorithm is the principle that at each moment, each particle adjusts its position in the search space based on the best position it has reached so far and the best position in its entire neighborhood. In this algorithm, each particle has a fitness value calculated by a fitness function. The closer a particle is to the goal in the search space, the higher its fitness value. Additionally, each particle has a velocity that governs its movement. By following the optimal particles in the current state, each particle continues its movement in the problem space. The start of the PSO optimization process involves the creation of a group of particles randomly, and by updating generations, attempts are made to find the optimal solution. In each step, each particle is updated using the two best values. The first is the best position that the particle has reached so far, represented by pbest, which is stored. The other best value used by the PSO algorithm is the best position obtained so far by the population of particles, represented by gbest. After finding the best values, the velocity and position of each particle are updated using equations (22) and (23).

$$v[] = v[] + (c1 * \text{rand}() * (\text{pbest}[] - \text{position}[])) + c2 * \text{rand}() * (\text{gbest}[] - \text{position}[]) \quad (22)$$

position[]

$$\text{position}[] = \text{position}[] + v[] \quad (23)$$

The right-hand side of equation (22) consists of three parts. The first part represents the current velocity of the particle, while the second and third parts are responsible for updating the particle's velocity and its rotation towards the best personal experience and the best group experience.

The pseudocode for the Particle Swarm Optimization algorithm is as follows:

Procedure ParticleSwarmOptimization()

 InitializeParticles()

While (not ReachedTerminationCriteria())

 For each particle in Population

 CalculateFitnessValue(particle)

 UpdatePersonalBest(particle)

 End For

UpdateGlobalBest()

```
For each particle in Population
  UpdateParticleVelocity(particle)
  UpdateParticlePosition(particle)
End For
End While
End Procedure
```

Procedure InitializeParticles()

```
For each particle in Population
  InitializePosition(particle)
  InitializeVelocity(particle)
  SetPersonalBest(particle)
End For
End Procedure
```

Function ReachedTerminationCriteria() : Boolean

```
If MaxIterationsReached() OR MinimumErrorCriteriaAchieved() Then
  Return True
Else
  Return False
End If
End Function
```

Procedure CalculateFitnessValue(particle)

```
Evaluate fitness value of the particle
End Procedure
```

Procedure UpdatePersonalBest(particle)

```
If CurrentFitnessValue(particle) is better than PersonalBestFitnessValue(particle) Then
  Set PersonalBestPosition(particle) to CurrentPosition(particle)
  Set PersonalBestFitnessValue(particle) to CurrentFitnessValue(particle)
End If
End Procedure
```

Procedure UpdateGlobalBest()

```
Set GlobalBestFitnessValue to the best fitness value among all particles
End Procedure
```

Procedure UpdateParticleVelocity(particl

```
For each dimension in Particle
```



```
    Update Velocity in dimension using equation (1)
  End For
End Procedure
```

```
Procedure UpdateParticlePosition(particle)
  For each dimension in Particle
    Update Position in dimension using equation (2)
  End For
End Procedure
```

The behavior of a particle swarm optimization algorithm is such that a group of particles (representing optimization variables) are dispersed in a search space. It is evident that some particles will have better positions compared to others. Therefore, based on the swarming behavior, the remaining particles attempt to bring their positions closer to those of the superior particles, while the positions of the superior particles are also changing. It is worth mentioning that the position change of each particle is based on its own experience in previous movements and the experience of neighboring particles. In fact, each particle is aware of its superiority or inferiority compared to its neighbors and the entire group.

To simulate this behavior, the following parameters are defined: a) Pbest: This parameter represents the best position that each particle can achieve during the algorithm execution. b) Gbest: This variable indicates the best positions that particles have achieved during the execution of the algorithm. c) Individual cognitive parameter (c₁): This quantity causes the particle to move towards the best point found by itself and its neighbors. This coefficient is used as a stimulation factor. d) Social cognitive parameter (c₂): This coefficient, also used as a stimulation factor, causes the particle to move towards the best point that particles have achieved so far. e) Inertia coefficient (w): This coefficient creates a balance between local search and global search in the algorithm. f) Velocity (v): This parameter represents the change in particle position in the search space.

Now, suppose the j-th particle has a dimension of g, which is expressed as equation (23):

$$X_j = [x_{j,1}, x_{j,2}, \dots, x_{j,g}] \quad (24)$$

Each particle has its own Pbest, and all particles share a common Gbest, defined as follows:

$$Pbest_{j,1}, Pbest_{j,2}, \dots, Pbest_{j,g}$$

Then, the change in particle position based on the value of velocity is given by equation (25):

$$v_{j,g}^{(t+1)} = wv_{j,g}c_1 \cdot \text{Rand}() (pbest_{j,g} - x_{j,g}^{(t)}) c_2 \cdot \text{rand}() \cdot (gbest_{j,g} - x_{j,g}^{(t)}), \quad (25)$$

$$v_{min} \leq v_{j,g}^{(t)} \leq v_{max}$$

$$x_{j,g}^{(t+1)} = x_{j,g}^{(t)} + v_{j,g}^{(t+1)} \quad j = 1, \dots, n \quad g = 1, \dots, m \quad (26)$$

In equations (4-4) and (4-5), the value of x represents the particle's position, n is the number of particles in the group, and m is the number of elements constituting the particle. The functions $\text{Rand}()$ and $\text{rand}()$ generate a random value between zero and one. It should be noted that setting a large value for v_{max} may cause particles to overshoot the minimum point, while setting it too small may result in the particle rotating around its position and not being able to explore the search space. The value of v_{max} is typically chosen within the range of 10% to 20% of the variable range. On the other hand, proper selection of w helps reduce the algorithm's iterations to reach the optimum point. In typical particle swarm optimization algorithms, the coefficient w decreases from 0.9 to 0.4 during the algorithm's execution, based on equation (27):

$$w = w_{max} - \frac{w_{max} - w_{min}}{iter_{max}} * iter \quad (27)$$

The cuckoo optimization algorithm is inspired by the life and reproduction behavior of a bird species called the cuckoo. The intriguing life and breeding habits of this bird hinted at a good optimization algorithm that operates with minimal effort, allowing survival in the struggle against other animals. The lazy cuckoo bird forces other birds to participate in its own survival by laying its eggs in their nests. For simplicity in describing the cuckoo search, the following three ideal laws are used:

1. Each cuckoo lays one egg at a time and places it in a randomly selected nest.
2. The best nests with high-quality eggs will be transferred to the next generation.
3. The number of available host nests is fixed, and the eggs laid by the cuckoos in the nest are discovered probabilistically by the host.

In this regard, the host bird may either escape from the foreign eggs or simply abandon the nest and build an entirely new nest. For the sake of implementation, the following simple representation can be considered, where each egg in a nest represents a candidate solution, and each cuckoo can only lay one egg. The goal is to use new and potentially better solutions (cuckoos) instead of not-so-good solutions in the nest.

This algorithm starts its work with an initial population, which consists of cuckoos. This population includes egg-laying cuckoos, which will be placed in a number of host nests. Some of these eggs, which bear a closer resemblance to the eggs of the host bird, have a better chance

of growing and becoming mature cuckoos. Other eggs are identified by the host bird and are removed. The number of grown eggs indicates the suitability of the nests in that area. The more eggs that can survive and be saved in an area, the more benefits that area receives. Therefore, the location where the maximum number of eggs survive will be a parameter that this algorithm seeks to optimize. Cuckoos search for the best area to maximize the survival of their eggs. When the cuckoo chicks grow and become mature, they live for a while in their environments and groups. However, when the time for egg-laying approaches, they migrate to better habitats where the chance of egg survival is higher. After forming cuckoo groups in different areas, the group with the best position is selected as the target point for other cuckoos to migrate to. During migration towards the target point, cuckoos do not traverse the entire path; they only travel part of the way and deviate from the path.

The results of the methods employed in the present study are presented in Table (2).

Table 2: Comparison of the Methods Employed in the Current Study

Algorithm	Error	Best Cost
Genetic Algorithm	0.1971	0.0029
Particle Swarm Optimization	0.1603	0.0012
Cuckoo Algorithm	0.1498	0.0006
Harris Hawk Algorithm	0.0950	0.0002

By comparing the numbers in Table 2, it can be concluded that the Harris Hawk Optimization algorithm performed better compared to other evolutionary algorithms used in the study.

Conclusion:

In the present study, the Harris Hawk Optimization algorithm was employed to improve vehicle routing in smart cities. The proposed solution consists of several phases aimed at minimizing costs and maximizing efficiency and utilization. Here, a quick guide and route planner for objects during movement (vehicles) have been provided. This is done considering various geographical conditions, traffic situations, different conditions of locations including availability and capacity for service provision, and other various factors. In other words, a vehicle intending to park can view route information and the current status of parking. A type of routing should be performed here that not only accelerates the response to objects but also has high efficiency. Therefore, this routing has been improved with the help of the evolutionary algorithm of Harris Hawks in several stages. The results obtained and the comparison with the methods of genetic algorithms, particle swarm optimization, and cuckoo algorithm indicate the desirability of the proposed method in optimizing routing costs in providing services to requesters.

Future Recommendations: Some of the suggestions for future work can be stated as follows:

- Using other evolutionary algorithms besides those used in the present study and comparing the results obtained with those of this research.
Using a combination of multiple evolutionary algorithms in the research field.

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